

STUDY OF ADHESIVE BONDED MID-PANEL CONNECTIONS
BETWEEN COMPOSITE PANELS

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ABSTRACT

Analytical expressions have been developed to predict the stress distribution in the adhesive layers of composite panel connections neglecting the membrane action of the panel facings. The stresses have also been studied experimentally by extrapolating the stresses obtained from photoelastic sheets mounted on the cover plates of the connection. Theoretical and experimental results compare favourably. The initial failure of the adhesive generally occurs at the ends of the cover plates where the stress values are maximum.

Introduction

The difference of physical properties at either side of the interface between adhesive and the adherend and geometric configurations of the connection will produce a varying intensity of stress concentration at the end of the bonded region.

Failure to recognize the significance of such stress concentrations has, in the past, led to some erroneous conclusions. It was customary to express the strength of a glued joint, for example, as an average breaking stress, i.e., the breaking load divided by the glue area. It was later found that stress concentrations due to the different layers of materials and to the shape and size of the test specimen caused premature local failures, thus limiting the strength of the whole joint.

The work presented herein identifies the location and intensity of such stress concentrations.

Historical Background

Numerous studies have been made of the design of adhesive-bonded connections. Lunsford (14) and Frey (6) have developed a theoretical analysis for the design of adhesive-bonded metal-to-metal joints. This work has been extended by Mylonas and DeBruyne (16) who have developed analytical expressions for analysing: (i) butt joints, (ii) scarf joints, (iii) lap joints, and (iv) double lap joints under various loading conditions. They have used the photoelastic method to analyze these joints experimentally. Ito (9) has carried out a detailed analysis of a lap joint under pure tension based on the theory of elasticity and subjected to various loading conditions. Kobatke and Inoue (10), (11) and (12) have discussed the stress distribution in an adhesive layer under tensile loading, and the residual stresses in adhesive layers and their evaluation. Panferov and Freidin (17) have studied and experimentally verified the effect of geometrical configuration in small laboratory specimens on the strength of glued joints of plastics and other structural materials. Segerlind (21) and Bryant and Dukes (3) have developed simplified mathematical relationships for calculating shearing stresses in adhesive joints, whereas, Perry (18) has developed simplified expressions for both normal and shear stress.

Theoretical Analysis of an Adhesive Bonded Joint

The type of joint selected for the theoretical analysis is shown in Fig. 1. In accordance with the assumptions generally made in composite construction, the bending moment is taken by the facings and the shear is transferred across the core through the tapered shear key. Normal stresses in the facings of one panel are transmitted to the respective facings of the second panel through the adhesive layer and the cover plate.

Assumptions:

- (i) The stress in the adhesive is assumed to have only two non-vanishing components, the normal stress $\bar{\sigma}$ and the shear stress $\bar{\tau}$, which vary negligibly across the small thickness of the bond.
- (ii) The aluminum sheets are supported elastically at the positions where the loads are applied. The condition of elastic support has the fixed-edge condition and the free-end condition as its limiting cases. Hence two separate theoretical analyses were carried out corresponding to each boundary condition. However, upon comparison

of the theoretical results with their experimental counterparts, it was found that the fixed-edge condition gave much closer results as compared to the free edge condition. Therefore, the following theoretical analysis is based on the fixed-edge condition at the ends of the pure moment regions. (The theoretical analysis corresponding to the free-edge condition is not included here because of length restriction.) Moreover, the fixed-edge condition seems to be justified in this case, in view of the restraining effect introduced in the surface of the facing by the applied loads. This restraint is better noticed at failure when delamination between core and facings occurs.

- (iii) The bending effect on the facings due to the shear stress τ between aluminum sheets and core is neglected.
- (iv) Deflections are assumed to be small, hence small deflection theory is used.
- (v) As shown in Fig. 2, we are considering two rectangular sheets of the same material of unit width and of lengths $2(a+b)$, and $2b$. The faces of the longer and shorter sheets of thickness f and ξf respectively, ($0 < \xi \leq 1$), are cemented together by an adhesive layer of thickness ψ , where ψ is small compared to f . The force T_f induced in the faces due to bending of the composite beam is considered per unit width. The stiffened structure is considered as a homogenous thin plate with finite discontinuities in its thickness and in its neutral plane. Bending of the neutral plane occurs under the applied loads; hence, a bending moment in addition to the normal force acts on the longer sheet at the bond edges.

The basic equations necessary for the solution of the problem are formulated within the framework of classical plate theory together with a system of sufficient boundary conditions.

Stress Resultants at the Bond Edges:

The composite plate shown in Fig. 2 will be considered as a homogeneous cylindrically-bent plate with a discontinuous thickness and neutral plane. For this calculation, since the thickness ψ of the adhesive layer is relatively small compared to the thickness f of the facings, the effect of adhesive thickness will be initially neglected. The loading T_f and M_f at the edges of the plate will produce a stress couple resultant $(M_2)_0$ acting on the facings at the bond edges. $(M_2)_0$ can be expressed in terms of the forces (T_f, M_f) and the physical dimensions of the plate, as shown below:

$$\frac{d^2w}{dx^2} = -\frac{M}{D} \quad (1)$$

which is the general expression relating curvature and bending moment, where

D, the flexural rigidity of the plate, is given by:

$$D = \frac{E_f \cdot t^3}{12(1 - \nu^2)} \quad (2)$$

where

E_f is the Young's Modulus for facings,
and ν is Poisson's ratio for the facings.

The deformation of the structure may be conveniently studied by separating it into regions 1 and 2 with coordinates (X_1, W_1) and (X_2, W_2) respectively, where both coordinate systems are fixed, as shown in Fig. 2. Then the bending moments acting at the generic sections of regions 1 and 2 are given by:

$$M_1 = -M_f + T_f w_1 \quad (0 < x_1 < a) \quad (3)$$

$$M_2 = -M_f + T_f \left(w_2 - \frac{\xi_f}{2} \right) \quad (a < x_2 < b) \quad (4)$$

where M_f is the moment in the facings at the concentrated loads P. In Eq. (4), the adhesive thickness ψ is neglected and the neutral axis of the facing is assumed to shift upward by half the thickness of the cover plate $\frac{t_f}{2}$ at the beginning of region 2. It should be noted that the length of region 2 (4 to 8 in.) is so large, relative to the facing thickness (0.025"), that the assumption made regarding the upward shifting of the neutral axis is not unrealistic.

Substituting Eqs. (3) and (4) into Eq. (1), respectively, and noting different flexural rigidities of $0 < x_1 < a$ and $a < x_2 < b$ from (2) due to different facing thickness, the following equations are obtained.

$$\frac{d^2 w_1}{dx_1^2} + \frac{T_f}{D} w_1 = \frac{M_f}{D} \quad (0 < x_1 < a) \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{d^2 w_2}{dx_2^2} - \frac{T_f}{(1 + \xi)^3 D} w_2 = \frac{1}{(1 + \xi)^3 D} \left\{ M_f + \frac{\xi_f \cdot T_f}{2} \right\} \quad (6)$$

(a < x_2 < b)

Eqs. (5) and (6) have general solutions

$$w_1 = A \operatorname{Sin} \left\{ \left(\frac{T_f}{D} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} x_1 \right\} + B \operatorname{Cos} \left\{ \left(\frac{T_f}{D} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} x_1 \right\} + \frac{M_f}{T_f} \quad (7)$$

$$w_2 = C \operatorname{Sin} \left\{ \left(\frac{T_f}{(1 + \xi)^3 D} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} x_2 \right\} + D \operatorname{Cos} \left\{ \left(\frac{T_f}{(1 + \xi)^3 D} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} x_2 \right\} + \frac{M_f}{T_f} + \frac{\xi f}{2} \quad (8)$$

The intermediate steps have been omitted for brevity. The constants of integration A, B, C, D and M_f are determined from the following five conditions:

$$\begin{aligned} @ x_1 = 0; w_1 = 0, \frac{dw_1}{dx_1} = 0 \\ @ x_1 = a \ \& \ x_2 = 0; w_1 = w_2 \ \& \ \frac{dw_1}{dx_1} = \frac{dw_2}{dx_2} \\ @ x_2 = b; \frac{dw_2}{dx_2} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

After the constants in Eqs. (7) and (8) have been determined by use of Eq. (9), the bending moment at the bond edges is given by: (assuming the continuity of stress resultants $(M_2)_0 = (M_1)_{\chi_1 = a} = (M_2)_{\chi_2 = 0}$)

$$(M_2)_0 = \frac{-\frac{\xi f}{2} \cdot T_f \cdot \operatorname{Sin} \left\{ \left(\frac{T_f}{(1 + \xi)^3 D} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} b \right\} \operatorname{Cos} \left\{ \left(\frac{T_f}{D} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} a \right\}}{\left(1 + \xi \right)^{3/2} \operatorname{Sin} \left\{ \left(\frac{T_f}{D} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} a \right\} \operatorname{Cos} \left\{ \left(\frac{T_f}{(1 + \xi)^3 D} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} b \right\} + \operatorname{Sin} \left\{ \left(\frac{T_f}{(1 + \xi)^3 D} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} b \right\} \operatorname{Cos} \left\{ \left(\frac{T_f}{D} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} a \right\}} \quad (10)$$

Eq. (10) applies to the moment $(M_2)_0$ in the connected facings of the compression side of the composite beam. For the tension side, the value of $(M_2)_0$ is the same in quantity, but opposite in sign.

Equations for Stresses δ and ζ in the Adhesive Layer:

We now consider the bonded region. The ends of the lower sheet, Fig. 3, are acted upon by a compressive force resultant T_f and by a bending moment resultant $(M_2)_0$ given by Eq. (10). Because the bond is considered in its undeformed state, symmetry requires the shear to vanish at the ends. The x-axis has its origin as shown and is directed positively to the right of Fig. 3.

According to the theory of cylindrically-bent plates, an element of the upper sheet will be acted upon by T_u and Q_u , the tensile and shear force resultants and by M_u , a bending moment resultant,

as shown in Fig. 4 (a). Counter-clockwise moments and downward forces are taken positive. Since the forces and moments are in equilibrium with the adhesive stresses $\bar{\sigma}$ and $\bar{\tau}$, the following equations hold:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dM_U}{dx} + Q_U + \frac{\tau \xi f}{2} &= 0 \\ \frac{dQ_U}{dx} + \bar{\sigma} &= 0 \\ \frac{dT_U}{dx} + \tau &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Similarly, if an element of the lower sheet (Fig. 4b) is considered, then for equilibrium, the following equations must be satisfied.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dM_L}{dx} + Q_L + \frac{\tau f}{2} &= 0 \\ \frac{dQ_L}{dx} - \bar{\sigma} &= 0 \\ \frac{dT_L}{dx} - \tau &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

If the positive transverse deflections of the neutral planes of the upper and lower sheets are denoted by w_U and w_L respectively, then from the Bernoulli's law

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d^2 w_U}{dx^2} &= -\frac{M_U}{\xi^3 D} \\ \frac{d^2 w_L}{dx^2} &= -\frac{M_L}{D} \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

If u_U and u_L are the longitudinal displacements of the lowermost and the uppermost fibres of the upper and lower sheets respectively, then

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{du_U}{dx} &= \frac{1}{E} \left\{ \frac{T_U}{\xi f} + \frac{6M_U}{\xi^2 f^2} \right\} \\ \frac{du_L}{dx} &= \frac{1}{E} \left\{ \frac{T_L}{f} - \frac{6M_L}{f^2} \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

finally, from the stress-strain relations for the adhesive we have

$$\frac{\tau}{G_c} = \frac{u_L - u_U}{\psi} \quad (15)$$

$$\frac{\bar{\sigma}}{E_c} = \frac{w_L - w_U}{\psi} \quad (16)$$

where E_c and G_c are the Young's and the shear moduli respectively for the adhesive and ψ is the thickness of the adhesive.

Equations for the determination of the adhesive stresses $\bar{\sigma}$ and $\bar{\tau}$ can now be formulated. Differentiating Eq. (15) and substituting Eq. (14) gives

$$\frac{d\tau}{dx} = \frac{G_c}{\psi E f} \left\{ \left(T_L - \frac{6M_L}{f} \right) - \frac{1}{\xi} \left(T_u + \frac{6M_u}{f} \right) \right\} \quad (17)$$

Differentiating Eq. (17) twice and substituting Eqs. (11) and (12) yields

$$\frac{d^3\tau}{dx^3} = \frac{G_c}{E f \psi} \left\{ \frac{4(1 + \xi)}{\xi} \frac{d\tau}{dx} + \frac{6\bar{\sigma}}{f} \frac{(1 - \xi^2)}{\xi^2} \right\} \quad (18)$$

In a similar manner, differentiating Eq. (16) and substituting Eq. (13), we obtain

$$\frac{d^2\bar{\sigma}}{dx^2} = \frac{E_c}{\psi D} \left(\frac{M_u}{\xi^3} - M_L \right) \quad (19)$$

Differentiating Eq. (19) twice and substituting Eqs. (11) and (12) gives

$$\frac{d^4\bar{\sigma}}{dx^4} = - \frac{E_c}{\psi D} \left\{ \frac{\bar{\sigma}(1 + \xi^3)}{\xi} + \frac{f}{2\xi^2} (\xi^2 - 1) \frac{d\tau}{dx} \right\} \quad (20)$$

Equations (18) and (20) form a pair of simultaneous, ordinary differential equations with constant coefficients for the determination of the stress distribution in the adhesive. Moreover, seven conditions are necessary with which to evaluate the seven arbitrary constants involved in the solution of Eqs. (18) and (20). The following physical conditions hold at the bond edges. (Refer to left-hand side of Fig. 3).

$$\begin{array}{ll} @ x = -\frac{b}{2} & @ x = \frac{b}{2} \\ M_u = Q_u = T_u = 0 & M_L = Q_L = T_L = 0 \\ M_L = (M_2)_0; T_L = T_f & T_u = T_f; M_u = (M_2)_0 \end{array} \quad (21)$$

Equivalently, by substituting Eqs. (21) into Eqs. (17) and (19) yields

$$\frac{d\tau}{dx} = \mp \frac{G_c}{\psi E f} \left(T_f - \frac{6(M_2)_0}{f} \right) \quad @ x = \pm \frac{b}{2} \quad (22)$$

$$\frac{d^2\bar{\sigma}}{dx^2} = \pm \frac{E_c}{\psi D} (M_2)_0 \quad @ x = \pm \frac{b}{2} \quad (23)$$

To Eqs. (22) and (23), the following equilibrium and symmetry conditions are added, assuming $\xi = 1$, that is when both plates are of equal thickness.

$$\int_{-b/2}^0 \tau \cdot dx = \frac{T_f}{2} \quad (24)$$

$$\int_{-b/2}^{+b/2} \delta \cdot dx = 0; \quad \delta \left(\frac{b}{2} \right) = \delta \left(-\frac{b}{2} \right) \quad (25)$$

Solution of the Differential Equations 18 and 20

The solution of Eqs. (18) and (20) for the adhesive stresses subject to Eqs. (22) to (25) will now be considered. When both sheets are of equal thickness ($\xi = 1$), Eqs. (18) and (20) reduce to

$$\frac{d^3 \tau}{dx^3} = \frac{8 G_c}{E \psi f} \frac{d\tau}{dx} \quad (26)$$

$$\frac{d^4 \delta}{dx^4} = -\frac{2 E_c}{\psi D} \delta \quad (27)$$

which are independent of each other.

The solution of Eq. (26) with boundary conditions specified by Eqs. (22) and (24) is

$$\begin{aligned} \tau = & \frac{\sqrt{2/4} \left(\frac{G_c}{E \psi f} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \left(T_f - \frac{6(M_2)_0}{f} \right) \text{Cosh} \left\{ 2\sqrt{2} \left(\frac{G_c}{E \psi f} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} x \right\}}{\text{Sinh} \left\{ 2\sqrt{2} \left(\frac{G_c}{E \psi f} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \frac{b}{2} \right\}} \\ & + \left[\left\{ 3 T_f + 6 \frac{(M_2)_0}{f} \right\} / 4b \right] \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

Equation (28) is plotted in Fig. 5. The solution of Eq. (27) under the conditions given by Eqs. (23) and (25) is

$$\begin{aligned} \delta = & -2 \left(\frac{E_c}{2\psi D} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} (M_2)_0 \left[\text{Sin} \left\{ \left(\frac{E_c}{2\psi D} \right)^{\frac{1}{4}} b + \text{Sinh} \left(\frac{E_c}{2\psi D} \right)^{\frac{1}{4}} b \right\} \right]^{-1} \\ & \times \left[\text{Cos} \left\{ \left(\frac{E_c}{2\psi D} \right)^{\frac{1}{4}} \frac{b}{2} \right\} \text{Sinh} \left\{ \left(\frac{E_c}{2\psi D} \right)^{\frac{1}{4}} \frac{b}{2} \right\} - \text{Sin} \left\{ \left(\frac{E_c}{2\psi D} \right)^{\frac{1}{4}} \frac{b}{2} \right\} \right. \\ & \text{Cos} \left\{ \left(\frac{E_c}{2\psi D} \right)^{\frac{1}{4}} \frac{b}{2} \right\} \text{Cos} \left\{ \left(\frac{E_c}{2\psi D} \right)^{\frac{1}{4}} x \right\} \text{Cosh} \left\{ \left(\frac{E_c}{2\psi D} \right)^{\frac{1}{4}} x \right\} \\ & + \text{Cos} \left\{ \left(\frac{E_c}{2\psi D} \right)^{\frac{1}{4}} \frac{b}{2} \right\} \text{Sinh} \left\{ \left(\frac{E_c}{2\psi D} \right)^{\frac{1}{4}} \frac{b}{2} \right\} + \text{Sin} \left\{ \left(\frac{E_c}{2\psi D} \right)^{\frac{1}{4}} \frac{b}{2} \right\} \\ & \left. \text{Cosh} \left\{ \left(\frac{E_c}{2\psi D} \right)^{\frac{1}{4}} \frac{b}{2} \right\} \text{Sin} \left\{ \left(\frac{E_c}{2\psi D} \right)^{\frac{1}{4}} x \right\} \text{Sinh} \left\{ \left(\frac{E_c}{2\psi D} \right)^{\frac{1}{4}} x \right\} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

Eq. (29) is plotted in Fig. 6.

The maximum values of ζ and σ occur at the boundaries and are given by the following expressions:

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_{\max} &= \sqrt{2/4} \left(\frac{G_c}{E \psi f} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \left(T_f - \frac{6(M_2)_0}{f} \right) \text{Coth} \left\{ 2\sqrt{2} \left(\frac{G_c}{E \psi f} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \frac{b}{2} \right\} \\ &\quad + \left[\left\{ 3 T_f + 6 \frac{(M_2)_0}{f} \right\} / 4b \right] \\ \sigma_{\max} &= \frac{- \left(\frac{E_c}{2 \psi D} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} (M_2)_0 \left[\text{Sinh} \left\{ \left(\frac{E_c}{2 \psi D} \right)^{\frac{1}{4}} b \right\} - \text{Sin} \left\{ \left(\frac{E_c}{2 \psi D} \right)^{\frac{1}{4}} b \right\} \right]}{\text{Sinh} \left\{ \left(\frac{E_c}{2 \psi D} \right)^{\frac{1}{4}} b \right\} + \text{Sin} \left\{ \left(\frac{E_c}{2 \psi D} \right)^{\frac{1}{4}} b \right\}} \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

Theoretical Calculation of ζ and σ in the Adhesive

Calculations of the stresses in the adhesive are made for typical values of the parameters in a stiffened plate. For the material of the cover plates, the values chosen are

$$E_f = 10.25 \times 10^6 \text{ psi}; \quad \nu = 0.33; \quad a = 2.0 \text{ in.}$$

$$b = 4 \text{ in.}; \quad f = 0.03 \text{ in.}; \quad \psi = 0.0128 \text{ in.}$$

For the bond, the material constants are

$$E_c = 516 \times 10^3 \text{ psi and } G_c = 184 \times 10^3 \text{ psi.}$$

which are representative values for Waldex W-105 adhesive (two component, 100% solids, epoxy resin/hardener system). In Fig. 5, the stress variation of ζ in the adhesive given by Eq. (28) is plotted for loads of 500, 750 and 1,000 lbs. on the beam. Fig. 6 illustrates the nature of σ variation for the same applied loads as given by Eq. (29). By using Eqs. (30), curves were plotted in Fig. 7 to relate maximum shear and normal stresses in the adhesive as functions of bond length.

Experimental Study of Adhesive Bonded Connections

In order to verify the results obtained from the theoretical analysis of adhesive-bonded joints in composite panels, five specimen joints were assembled and tested. Each consisted of a beam 2 ft. long, 3 3/4 in. wide and 1 3/4 in. thick made up of honeycomb cores and of aluminum facings with a double tapered wooden shear key in the middle of it, as shown in Fig. 1. In order to transfer forces of the facings across the joint, aluminum cover plates were bonded to the facings using Waldex W-105 adhesive.

Joints thus assembled were tested in four-point flexural loading test, as shown in Fig. 8, for three different loads, i.e., 500, 750 and 1,000 lbs.

The standard photoelastic method of analysis was used to analyse the stress distribution on the cover plates. Photostress plastic sheets were bonded to the cover plates using reflective adhesive and cured at room temperature. Photographs were taken of isoclinics for angle settings of 0° , 30° , 45° , 60° , and 90° on the polariscope dial, and of isochromatics of half and integral order for each of the three different loads per specimen. This data was used to determine shear stress (γ) and the normal stress (σ) in the plane of the cover plate using the standard shear difference method. These stresses were then linearly extrapolated to determine their respective values in the plane of the adhesive, which have been plotted in Figs. 9 and 10.

Discussion and Conclusion

The yielding of the adhesive will occur at the bond edges where the maximum stresses occur. (Figs. 5, 6, 9 and 10). Although σ_{\max} is slightly less than γ_{\max} , σ_{\max} produces yielding in the case of Waldex W-105 since this adhesive has a yield stress of approximately 2485 psi in shear as compared to 1250 psi in tension.

The plot of maximum shear and normal stresses in the adhesive versus the bond length (Fig. 7) reveals that the magnitude of these stresses remains almost constant for bond lengths higher than about one and two inches respectively.

Theoretical and experimental values for shear stresses can be compared from graphs in Figs. 5 and 9. The maximum percentage difference is about 18% and it occurs at the bond ends with theoretical values being higher.

Theoretical and experimental values for normal stress (Figs. 6 and 10) cannot be compared directly since the theoretical values are normal to the plane of the adhesive layer and the experimental values are in the adhesive plane. However, there seems to be a close relationship between the two.

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Nomenclature

a, b	Lengths as shown, in.
D	Flexural rigidity of the cover plates.
E_f	Young's modulus for facings.
f	Thickness of aluminum sheet, in.
M_L, M_U	Moments in lower and upper sheets.
$(M_2)_0$	Moment at the bond edges due to eccentricity.
P	Concentrated loads, lbs.
T_f	Axial compressive force in aluminum facings, lbs.
w	Deflection of the plate, in.
w_1, w_2	Deflections of the plate, in.
ξf	Thickness of the cover plate, in.
σ	Normal stress, psi.
τ	Shear stress, psi.
ν	Poisson's ratio for facings.
ψ	Thickness of glue line, in.

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1. Adhesive Bonded Tapered Joint.

2. Detail A.

3. Bonded Region Showing Applied Loads.

(a) UPPER SHEET

(b) LOWER SHEET

4. Stresses on an Element of Bonded Region.

SET-UP FOR FLEXURAL TEST

SKETCH SHOWING COVER PLATE BONDED TO ALUMINUM FACINGS

5. Theoretical Distribution of Shear Stress in Adhesive Layer on the Compression Side of Specimen.

SET UP FOR FLEXURAL TESTING

SYMMETRICAL ABOUT

SKETCH SHOWING COVER PLATE BONDED TO ALUMINUM FACINGS

6. Theoretical Distribution of Normal Stress (Normal to the Plane of the Adhesive) in Adhesive on the Compression Side of Specimen.

7. Maximum Shear and Normal Stresses in the Adhesive as Functions of Bond Length on the Compression Side of Specimen.

8. Experimental Set-up of an Adhesive Bonded Connection Tested in Flexure Under Four Point Loading.

SET-UP FOR FLEXURAL TESTING

SKETCH SHOWING COVER PLATE BONDED TO ALUMINUM FACINGS

9. Experimental Distribution of Shear Stress in the Adhesive Layer on the Compression Side of Specimen for 500, 750 and 1,000 lbs. of Load.

10. Experimental Distribution of Normal Stress (in the Plane of Adhesive) in the Adhesive Layer on the Compression Side of Specimen for 500, 750 and 1,000 lbs. of Load.

Discussion by Kenneth G. Kreider, National Bureau of Standards
Rapporteur, International Conference on Composite Materials, 1975

Analytical expressions were developed to predict the stress distribution in the adhesive layers of composite panel connections neglecting the membrane action of the panel facings. The stresses were also determined experimentally by extrapolating the stresses obtained from photoelastic sheets mounted on the cover plates of the connection. Theoretical and experimental results compare favorably. The initial failure of the adhesive generally occurs at the ends of the cover plates where the stress values are maximum.

The type of joint selected for the theoretical analysis is shown in **Figure 2**. In accordance with the assumptions generally made in composite construction, the bending moment is taken by the facings and the shear is transferred across the core through the tapered shear key. Normal stresses in the facings of one panel are transmitted to the respective facings of the second panel through the adhesive layer and the cover plate.

Conclusion

The yielding of the adhesive is predicted to occur at the bond edges where the maximum stresses occur. Although σ_{\max} is slightly less than τ_{\max} , σ_{\max} produced yielding in the case of Waldex W-105 since this adhesive has a yield stress of approximately 2485 psi in shear as compared to 1250 psi in tension.

The plot of maximum shear and normal stresses in the adhesive versus the bond length (**Figure 7**) reveals that the magnitude of these stresses remains almost constant for bond lengths higher than about one and two inches respectively.

Theoretical and experimental values for shear stresses between the maximum percentage difference is about 18% and it occurs at the bond ends with theoretical values being higher.